

Graphite and multi-layer graphene from a low molecular weight carbon source

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ABSTRACT

While carbonaceous structures formed by pyrolysis of macromolecular carbon sources with silicates are well described in the literature, information on the structure of carbons obtained in the similar way from low molecular weight (LMW) carbon sources is not sufficient. This study is therefore aimed at characterizing the material obtained by pyrolyzing (1300 °C; Ar atmosphere) montmorillonite containing ~25–50 wt% LMW cations as a carbon source. Pyrolyzed samples contained ~5–20 wt% carbon, and thermogravimetric and elemental analysis showed a higher yield for a higher original amount of the LMW carbon source. In addition to amorphous carbon, graphite was formed during pyrolysis, as confirmed by X-ray diffraction analysis, Raman spectroscopy, and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. The presence of graphene-based nanomaterial, specifically multi-layer graphene, was revealed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Electrical conductivity of the silicate/carbon material reached ~35 S m⁻¹. Raman spectra and TEM images are similar to those from studies describing the use of macromolecular carbon sources. LMW compounds are a sufficient source of carbon for the preparation of electrically conductive materials containing graphite and multi-layer graphene.

1. Introduction

Graphene is a carbon allotrope formed by a monoatomic layer of hexagonally arranged carbon atoms with sp² hybridization, and graphene layer is the basic building block of graphite [1]. Graphene and graphene-based materials (GBM) have attracted the scientific community with their unique electrical, optical, mechanical or thermal properties [2–4]. In view of the many potential practical applications, (sensing [4,5], catalysis [2], electromagnetic shielding [6], strengthening of materials [7], antibacterial effect [8], energy storage [4,9], or solar cells [4] to name a few), attention was focused not only to the preparation of pure material (by methods other than bulk graphite disintegration [10,11]), but also to the preparation of composites containing graphene or GBM as one of two or more components. Aside from mixing the matrix with pre-prepared, commercially available graphene, GBM or graphite [7,12–16], another widely used route is the preparation *in situ*, either directly from e.g. carbides or carbonitrides using

selective extraction or spark plasma sintering [17–20], or by applying high temperatures (e.g. pyrolysis [21], hot-pressing [22] or spark plasma sintering [23]) to inorganic matrices mixed, surface modified or intercalated with organic compounds. In the case of layered materials, natural clay minerals are often used for this purpose [24]. A wide range of synthetic and natural macromolecules has been reported as a carbon source. The most common inorganic matrix was montmorillonite (MMT) (for polyacrylonitrile [25–27], polystyrene [28,29], polyvinyl alcohol [30], resol-F127 block copolymer [31], polyethylene terephthalate [28], polyvinyl acetate [32], polyfurfuryl alcohol [32–34], pyrene-trioxane copolymer [35,36], polybenzimidazole [37], sucrose [38–41], polyaniline [42–44], polypyrrole [45]). But also sepiolite (SEP) (for polyacrylonitrile [46], polypropylene [47], sucrose [48–50], gelatin [50]), talc (for polyethylene terephthalate or polystyrene [28]), saponite (SAP) (for polyfurfuryl alcohol [51]), halloysite (for sucrose [52,53]), taeniolite (TAE) (for polyfurfuryl alcohol [54,55]), attapulgite (for maltose [56]), laponite (for starch [57]), porous alumina (for

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polyvinyl alcohol [58]), yttria-stabilized zirconia (for cellulose [23,59]) and layered double hydroxide (LDH) (for polyfurfuryl alcohol [33]) were reported. Petroleum oily sludge (used with MMT [21]) and coal-tar pitch (used with petroleum coke [22]) can also be included among these macromolecular carbon sources. Heat treatment of macromolecules with inorganic matrix often leads to the formation of GBM [22,23,26,28,31,37,40–45,48–50,54,58,59] or graphite [21,22,25,27,32,46,52,60]. Although in some studies the inorganic matrix serves just for templating, i.e. after heat treatment, the matrix is removed and attention is subsequently paid only to the pure carbonaceous component prepared from the macromolecular compound [25–29,32,35,36,38,41,42,53–57], many studies are focused directly on composites of carbon/inorganic matrix type [21–23,30,31,33,34,37,40,43–52,58,59]. These composites usually exhibit good electrical conductivity [21–23,31,37,43–46,50,56,58,59] and are therefore useable e.g. as electrodes [23,31,37,46,50,56], or have a large surface area suitable for utilization in gas adsorption [30,33,34,49] or wastewater treatment [52,57].

The situation in the case of using low molecular weight organic compounds as carbon sources is quite interesting. Various authors have investigated this route, and heated materials intercalated with small molecules. MMT again dominated as a matrix (for pyrene [29,35,36,61–63], styrene [35,36], ethylene [35,36], propylene [35,36], naphthalene [29], acrylonitrile [63], furfuryl alcohol [63], vinyl acetate [63], ionic liquids [60], acriflavine [64], aminoacridine [64], safranin [64], indole blue [64]), followed by TAE (for pyrene [65], acriflavine [64], aminoacridine [64], safranin [64,65], indole blue [64,65]), SEP (for ethylene or propylene [66]), and LDH (for 3-sulfopropylmethacrylic acid [67]). However, it is surprising that the authors do not mention formation of graphene or GBM. They obtained graphite [60], microcrystalline graphite within amorphous carbon [63,67], spherical assemblage of quasigraphitic crystallites [35,36], layered carbon particles with holes [29], carbon tubes with little or no graphitic character [66], amorphous carbon [62], carbon [61], char [65], or carbon very far from ideal graphene [64]. This is in contrast to the macromolecular sources often leading to GBM, as mentioned above. The answer to the question of whether a low molecular weight organic compound in the presence of a silicate matrix can be used to obtain GBM is not clear. Our interest is to find the answer because the possibility of obtaining GBM from low molecular weight carbon sources, i.e. omitting the polymerization step (if the source of carbon is not natural macromolecule), means simplifying the preparation process. Knowing whether low molecular weight organic compounds can be an alternative to macromolecular sources in the preparation of GBM could also be useful in deciding the further use of some waste materials, e.g. clay-based adsorbents containing small organic molecules.

It should also be noted that the matrix is routinely removed in studies dealing with low molecular weight sources (an exception can be found in Takahashi et al. [60]). Insufficient information on the carbon/inorganic matrix composites prepared using low molecular weight carbon sources is another reason to pay attention to this topic.

Our study is focused on characterization of carbon/silicate composites prepared using small molecules as carbon sources. We have previously described the successful preparation of electrically conductive composites containing GBM formed from polyaniline in the presence of MMT [43,44]. More regular arrangement of polyaniline chains on the surface or in the MMT interlayer space (compared to pure polyaniline) has been cited as one of the reasons for the transformation of polyaniline to GBM. By using only the anilinium sulfate precursor, we also want to find out whether this condition is necessary to get the GBM. Preparation procedure described in our earlier studies is retained here with the difference that the anilinium is not polymerized, but the anilinium/MMT intercalate is directly pyrolyzed. To ensure maximum simplicity of the preparation, no additional procedures such as clay organophilization [40] or pillaring [29,30,33–36,55,61,62] are used.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Aniline ($C_6H_5NH_2$; pure) and sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4 ; p. a., 96 %) were purchased from Lach-Ner, Czech Republic, and used as received without further purification. Sodium-rich montmorillonite (MMT) Portaclay® having crystallochemical formula $(Al_{2.85}Mg_{0.71}Ti_{0.02}Fe_{0.42}^{3+})(Si_8O_{20}(OH)_4)$ with a layer charge of ~ 0.7 el. per unit cell [45] was purchased from Ankerpoort NV, Netherlands. Without any purification, the MMT was ground and sieved to obtain the $<40 \mu m$ size fraction used in this study.

2.2. Preparation procedure

Anilinium sulfate was prepared from aniline and sulfuric acid aqueous solution ($C_{H_2SO_4} = 0.5 \text{ mol l}^{-1}$). In this process, the aniline is protonated by the acid to form anilinium ($C_6H_5-NH_3^+$). Mixing 1.75, 3.5, 5.25, and 7.0 ml of the aniline with 98.25, 96.5, 94.75, and 93 ml of the acid solution, respectively (stirred for 10 min using Heidolph MR HeiMIX S magnetic stirrer at room temperature), led to four anilinium sulfate solutions with concentrations of 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, and 0.8 mol l^{-1} , respectively. In the next step, 4 g of MMT was added to each solution and allowed to intercalate for 7 days at room temperature. The pH of the intercalation solutions was in the range of 1–3. Acidic environment does not cause a change in the MMT composition and structure [68], but it leads to protonation of MMT edges, which, together with the negative layer charge, leads to face-to-edge interaction of MMT particles and thus to reduced accessibility of the interlayer space [69]. Therefore, a longer than usual intercalation time was chosen. However, it should be noted that also 8 days [32] or 13 days [54] were reported.

The resulting intercalates were collected on filters, washed with distilled water, and finally dried at $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Memmert UNE 40 hot air dryer) for 24 h. Such obtained powder samples, denoted as 0.2An_MMT, 0.4An_MMT, 0.6An_MMT, and 0.8An_MMT, were pressed at room temperature into tablets ($28 \times 28 \times 2 \text{ mm}$) using the HJC12 Plus, uni-max table hydraulic press. Pressure of 25 MPa was applied for 10 min. No binder was used. Pyrolysis was carried out under the same conditions as in our previous study [45], i.e. at a temperature of $1300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in tube resistance furnace ($V = 2.26 \text{ dm}^3$; CLASIC CZ s. r.o., Czech Republic) under argon atmosphere ($>99.9999 \text{ } \%$ Ar; $p = 1.06 \cdot 10^5 \text{ Pa}$). Heating up to $1300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was controlled by Rh/Pt-13 % thermocouple (heating rate of $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$), the tablets were exposed to the target temperature of $1300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h, and then cooled ($-5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$). The inert atmosphere was replaced (Ar flow of $5 \text{ dm}^3 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ for 5 min) at a temperature of $900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $1100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $1300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and before the start of cooling. Tablets were pressed to prevent the powder from being blown around and thus lost during exchanges of the Ar atmosphere.

2.3. Characterization methods

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed using STA 409 EP thermogravimeter (Netzsch, Germany) equipped with highly sensitive analytical balances. Each sample ($\sim 20 \text{ mg}$) was inserted into $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ crucible and heated up to $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$) in a dynamic ($100 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) argon atmosphere ($>99.999 \text{ } \%$ Ar). Mass percentages of anilinium sulfate ($w_{An,S-TGA}$; wt.%) in An_MMT samples was determined using the following equation

$$w_{An,S-TGA} = 100 \cdot (\Delta m_{An_MMT} - \Delta m_{MMT}) / (\Delta m_{An} - \Delta m_{MMT}) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where Δm_{An_MMT} , $\Delta m_{An,S-TGA}$, and Δm_{MMT} is a mass loss in wt.% of An_MMT intercalate, pure anilinium sulfate and pure MMT, respectively. Temperature range of $40\text{--}990 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was used for the calculation. Eq. (1) is based on the method used by Marins et al. [70] that both components in a composite produce an amount of residue proportional to the

Fig. 1. (a) Mass losses of An_MMT samples and pure components, i.e. MMT and anilinium sulfate (An_S), before pyrolysis, as obtained by TGA. (b) XRPD patterns of the An_MMT samples and the pure components before pyrolysis. (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

amount of each component.

X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) patterns were obtained by Miniflex600 powder diffractometer (Rigaku, Japan) equipped with Co lamp ($\lambda_{\text{Co}, K\alpha} = 1.7889 \text{ \AA}$) and DTex/Ultra 1D detector. Symmetrical Bragg-Brentano arrangement and reflection mode were used. The diffractograms were recorded in the range of $5\text{--}60^\circ 2\theta$ (step size and time of 0.02° and $5^\circ \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, respectively), and the phase composition of samples was determined using PDXL-2 Release 2019 database.

Force field-based molecular modeling was performed in Materials Studio (Biovia, USA). MMT unit cell ($(\text{Al}_2)(\text{Si}_4)\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH})_2$) having lattice parameters $a = 5.18 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 8.97 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 13.9 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 99.6^\circ$, $\gamma = 90^\circ$ [71], was enlarged into $3a \times 6b \times 1c$ supercell $(\text{Al}_{72})(\text{Si}_{144})\text{O}_{360}(\text{OH})_{72}$ and its composition was modified as follows: $(\text{Al}_{51}\text{Mg}_{13}\text{Fe}_8^{3+})(\text{Si}_{144})\text{O}_{360}(\text{OH})_{72}$. Atomic charges were determined by the QEq method [72]. Layer charge of the supercell structure ($x = -13 \text{ el.}$) was compensated by interlayer cations and anilinium molecules in various ratios. Water molecules were also added to the interlayer space. All atoms were parameterized by Universal force field [73], and the models with fixed lattice parameters a , b , γ were optimized using Smart algorithm, as available in Forcite module (convergence criteria: $E = 1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, $F = 0.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1} \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, $d = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ \AA}$). Basal spacings (d_{001} values) of the optimized models was determined in Reflex module using simulated XRPD performed under the same conditions as the real XRPD analysis.

Amount of carbon, nitrogen and sulfur in samples was determined by CHNS analysis performed in Elementar vario EL Cube analyser (Elementar, Germany). Concurrent analysis of standard (4-Aminobenzenesulfonic acid, 5 mg) was performed to ensure accuracy $<0.1 \text{ wt \%}$ for each element.

Raman spectra were obtained by 180-degree measurement technique using DXR SmartRaman dispersive spectrometer (ThermoScientific, USA) equipped with 780 nm laser and CCD detector using a

backscattering configuration. Grating, aperture, and exposure time (100 exposures) was $400 \text{ lines} \cdot \text{mm}^{-1}$, 50 \mu m , and 1 s , respectively. An empty sample compartment was used for background measurement. Fluorescence was corrected using spectral software OMNIC (v.9.2; Thermo Scientific, USA).

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) apparatus consisting of SPECS PHOIBOS 100 hemispherical analyser with a 5-channel detector and a SPECS XR50 M/FOCUS500 monochromatic X-ray source equipped with an Al and Ag dual anode was used to analyse the samples' surface composition and the chemical state of the elements. The Al anode at $E_{\text{pass}} 40 \text{ eV}$ and 10 eV was used for survey and high-resolution spectra, respectively. The spectra were collected in a normal direction and a sample charge was compensated during the measurements by SPECS FG22/35. The analyser was set to work in Fixed Analyser Transmission mode and Medium Area (Magnification $M = 5$) settings with entrance slit $7 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$ and Iris diameter 35 mm , i.e. the measured area was about $1.4 \times 4 \text{ mm}^2$. The pressure was kept under $7 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ Pa}$ during the measurements. The acquired data were processed in CasaXPS software with Shirley background profile and built-in RSF was used for the calculation of the elemental composition. The samples were measured as received. The UPS technique is not available in the instrument. Morphology was studied using transmission electron microscope JEOL 2010 HC (JEOL Ltd., Japan) at an accelerating voltage of 160 kV and with LaB_6 as the source of electrons. Measurements of distances on images taken with the microscope were performed using ImageJ software [74].

2.4. Electrical conductivity measurements

DC conductivity measurement of samples in powder form was carried out under the same conditions and using the same equipment (DC POWER SUPPLY HY 3003 D-2, programmable DC POWER SUPPLY BK

Table 1

Elemental analysis (in wt.%) of samples before pyrolysis. For each sample, two measurements, probe 1 (-p1) and probe 2 (-p2), were performed. The C/N (w/w) ratio was determined for all samples. Amount of anilinium sulfate (w_{An_S} ; in wt.%) was calculated as a sum of all listed elements. Amount of anilinium (w_{An} ; in wt.%) was calculated as a sum of all listed elements except sulfur. Amount of anilinium sulfate as determined by TGA ($w_{\text{An}_S\text{-TGA}}$; in wt.%) is also listed for comparison.

	N	C	H	S	C/N	w_{An_S}	w_{An}	$w_{\text{An}_S\text{-TGA}}$
0.2An_MMT-p1	2.34	12.18	2.18	3.31	5.21	20.01	16.70	21.78
0.2An_MMT-p2	2.36	12.34	2.18	3.32	5.23	20.20	16.88	21.78
0.4An_MMT-p1	3.47	17.62	2.47	4.27	5.08	27.83	23.56	29.01
0.4An_MMT-p2	3.44	17.55	2.46	4.27	5.10	27.71	23.45	29.01
0.6An_MMT-p1	3.93	20.18	2.65	4.46	5.13	31.21	26.75	31.55
0.6An_MMT-p2	3.89	20.14	2.64	4.47	5.18	31.13	26.67	31.55
0.8An_MMT-p1	5.94	30.52	3.68	6.56	5.14	46.70	40.14	48.47
0.8An_MMT-p2	5.98	30.73	3.70	6.60	5.14	47.01	40.41	48.47

Fig. 2. The MMT d_{001} values (black diamonds) obtained by simulated XRPD from the optimized models of samples before pyrolysis with various interlayer content (An – anilinium cation, Na – sodium cation, S – sulfate anion, H₂O – water molecule). Average of experimentally determined d_{001} values (12.05 Å; see Fig. 1b) is provided as the horizontal red line. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

PRECISION 9120, pA-meter KEITHLEY 6487) as in our previous study [45]. The samples before pressing and pyrolysis are in powder form (see section 2.2). In the case of pyrolyzed samples, the fine powder was prepared from pyrolyzed tablets by crushing them by pestle in porcelain mortar. The powder was then placed between two rod Cu electrodes in a vertical glass tube (internal diameter 3.9 mm). Each sample was measured fifteen times, and the electrical current under constant voltage was recorded for 300 s. The average value of electrical current was used to calculate the electrical conductivity σ (S·m⁻¹) using the following equation:

$$\sigma_{pow} = (I / U) \cdot (d / S) \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where I is electrical current (A), U is voltage (V), d is distance between electrodes, i.e. height of the powder column (m), and S is circular cross-sectional area of electrode (m²).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structure and composition of samples before pyrolysis

Calculation according to Eq. (1) and based on data obtained by thermogravimetric analysis of An_MMT samples and pure components (Fig. 1a) revealed amount of the anilinium sulfate ($w_{\text{An,S-TGA}}$) to be in good agreement with the total amount of C, H, N, S obtained from the elemental analysis (compare $w_{\text{An,S-TGA}}$ and $w_{\text{An,S}}$ in Table 1). Average amount of anilinium (w_{An}) in samples 0.2An_MMT, 0.4An_MMT, 0.6An_MMT, and 0.8An_MMT is 16.78, 23.50, 26.71, and 40.27 wt%, respectively. Considering the original amount of aniline in the solutions used for the preparation of An_MMT samples (see Table S1), approximately one half (53.4 ± 6.1 %) was adsorbed by the MMT.

The average value of the C/N ratio (5.15 ± 0.05; see Table 1) does not allow to distinguish between anilinium and polyaniline (the C/N ratio for each of these compounds is 5.14). However, formation of polyaniline in acidic environment results in a dark green coloration [75]. No color change in samples 0.2An_MMT - 0.8An_MMT and no electrical conductivity of these samples confirm the preservation of anilinium in its original state without polymerization to polyaniline.

XRPD analysis (Fig. 1b) shows no significant changes in positions of MMT reflections for An_MMT samples, proving that the MMT structure

was not affected by pH during the preparation procedure (see section 2.2). In the case of MMT basal reflection (001), the increase in intensity and thinning can be seen in XRPD patterns of all An_MMT samples (Fig. 1b). For a detailed comparison, see Supplementary material (Fig. S1). A similar change in the shape and intensity of the MMT basal reflection was previously observed for polyaniline/MMT nanocomposite and was interpreted as more ordered MMT layers due to intercalation [76,77]. Unlike polyaniline intercalation [76,77], however, the basal spacings of An_MMT samples ($d_{001} = 12.05 \pm 0.03$ Å; Fig. 1b) do not differ much from the d_{001} value of pure MMT (12.07 Å; Fig. 1b). However, this may not be a reason to exclude the possibility of intercalation. Molecules can enter the interlayer space and not cause an increase in the original basal spacing if they are sufficiently small or flat compared to the original interlayer content (in this case the hydrated Na⁺ cations). Some authors even report a decrease in d_{001} after intercalation (e.g. caffeine in MMT [78], hydrazine in MMT [79], or octadecyltrimethylammonium in MMT [80]). In order to determine whether intercalation could have occurred even with an almost unchanged d_{001} value, the MMT interlayer space content was studied using force field-based molecular modeling, which has previously proven to be an effective tool for studying nanocomposites of this type [81–83].

While pure MMT contains only interlayer Na⁺ cations and water (Fig. S2a), the entry of anilinium cations leads to a wide range of variations in the content of the interlayer space. The MMT d_{001} values corresponding to the optimized models with various interlayer content (Fig. 2) show that the simple replacement of 13 Na⁺ cations (layer charge of the MMT supercell structure is -13 el.; see section 2.3) by 13 anilinium cations is not in agreement with the experimentally determined basal spaces (Fig. 1b; see also red line in Fig. 2).

Combining 1–3 Na⁺ cations with 16–18 anilinium cations and 2–3 sulfate anions (compensating the charge of excessive cations), three models (Fig. 2) exhibiting d_{001} values very close to the experimentally determined d_{001} values were found: 16An 3S 3Na 6H₂O (Fig. S2b), 17An 3S 2Na (Fig. S2c), and 18An 3S 1Na (Fig. S2d). Therefore, intercalation can be considered possible despite the negligible changes in the d_{001} values (Fig. 1b). With respect to the composition of the MMT supercell structure (see section 2.3) and with respect to the amount of Na⁺ cations, sulfate anions and water molecules present, the numbers of anilinium cations in these three models correspond to 9.9, 10.6, and 11.2 wt

Table 2

Elemental analysis (in wt.%) of pyrolyzed samples and the corresponding C/N (w/w) ratios. Amount of carbonaceous part (w_{CP} ; in wt.%) was calculated as a sum of all listed elements (Σ) except sulfur. For each sample, two measurements, probe 1 (-p1) and probe 2 (-p2), were performed. For comparison, average amount of anilinium (w_{An} , in wt.%) in samples before pyrolysis (Table 1) and w_{An}/w_{CP} ratios are also listed.

	N	C	H	S	Σ	C/N	w_{CP}	w_{An}	w_{An}/w_{CP}
0.2An_MMT-p1	0.17	4.71	0.19	0.20	5.27	27.71	5.07	16.79	3.31
0.2An_MMT-p2	0.16	4.66	0.19	0.20	5.21	29.13	5.01	16.79	3.35
0.4An_MMT-p1	0.21	6.51	0.18	0.35	7.25	31.00	6.90	23.50	3.41
0.4An_MMT-p2	0.22	6.43	0.19	0.35	7.19	29.23	6.84	23.50	3.44
0.6An_MMT-p1	0.26	9.69	0.18	0.20	10.33	37.27	10.13	26.71	2.64
0.6An_MMT-p2	0.27	9.80	0.18	0.21	10.46	36.30	10.25	26.71	2.61
0.8An_MMT-p1	0.37	20.04	0.21	0.47	21.09	54.16	20.62	40.27	1.95
0.8An_MMT-p2	0.37	19.82	0.22	0.47	20.88	53.57	20.41	40.27	1.97

Fig. 3. (a) XRPD patterns (1 – low cristobalite, 2 – mullite, 3 – graphite) and (b) Raman spectra of the pyrolyzed An_MMT samples. (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

% of anilinium, respectively, i.e. 10.6 ± 0.5 wt% in average. In each sample, this amount of anilinium can be present in the MMT interlayer space. As the total amount of anilinium in the samples increases, its fraction in the MMT interlayer space decreases, while the fraction outside the MMT interlayer space increases. The XRPD analysis do not contradict this assumption. Pure anilinium sulfate is crystalline (Fig. 1b) and the presence of its reflections in the XRPD patterns of samples with a higher An content (0.6An_MMT a 0.8An_MMT; see black arrows in Fig. 1b) suggests that the anilinium (as sulfate) is also deposited outside the interlayer space, i.e. on the MMT surface and between its particles.

3.2. Structure and composition of pyrolyzed samples

As determined by TGA, mass losses of all four pyrolyzed samples were negligible (0.66 ± 0.21 wt%) in the entire temperature range. The amount of carbonaceous part (w_{CP}) was determined from elemental analysis of pyrolyzed samples (Table 2). Comparison of w_{An} with w_{CP} revealed the effect of the anilinium content in samples before pyrolysis on carbonaceous content in pyrolyzed samples. While in the case of 0.2An_MMT the w_{CP} corresponds to $\sim 1/3$ of the w_{An} , for 0.8An_MMT the w_{CP} is only ~ 2 times lower compared to w_{An} (Table 2). These results indicate a higher yield of the pyrolysis for a higher original amount of anilinium. Graphs of interdependencies of the input amount of aniline, w_{An} in samples before pyrolysis, and w_{CP} in pyrolyzed samples are provided in Supplementary material (Fig. S3).

Very high values of C/N ratio (Table 2) compared to the values found for samples before pyrolysis (Table 1) can be explained by the transition of nitrogen to the gas phase during pyrolysis. This is presumable given the observation reported in our earlier study [45] where the NH_4Cl was found in the furnace after pyrolysis. The source of chlorine was the

oxidizing agent $FeCl_3$ used to polymerize pyrrole into polypyrrole [45]. If the nitrogen escaped from the polypyrrole, in which it is part of the heterocycle, it can be assumed that it could easily escape from anilinium, where it is in the form of $-NH_3^+$ functional group. The absence of $FeCl_3$ in the present study probably caused that the nitrogen released during pyrolysis in the form of ammonia escaped into the Ar atmosphere and was removed with it. The C/N ratio values for pyrolyzed samples (Table 2) increase continuously from ~ 28 (0.2An_MMT) to ~ 54 (0.8An_MMT), i.e. the lower the amount of anilinium in the samples before pyrolysis, the higher the amount of nitrogen in the samples after pyrolysis and vice versa. This may be due to the intercalated anilinium in the samples before pyrolysis. According to the molecular modeling (see section 3.1), the highest and lowest fraction of intercalated anilinium can be assumed for 0.2An_MMT and 0.8An_MMT, respectively. The lowest C/N ratio for 0.2An_MMT can thus be explained by the more difficult release of nitrogen from the intercalated anilinium, while the highest C/N ratio for 0.8An_MMT can be explained by the easier release of nitrogen from anilinium on the MMT surface.

XRPD patterns of pyrolyzed samples revealed the presence of three phases: low cristobalite (PDF No. 01-076-0941), mullite (PDF No. 01-079-1457), and graphite (PDF No. 00-026-1079) (Fig. 3a). While the first two phases are the result of MMT thermal transformation [21,29,43,45], the presence of the third phase can be explained by the successful transformation of at least part of the anilinium into a graphitic structure. The anilinium molecules lying almost parallel to the MMT layers are oriented towards each other by their edges (Fig. S2), which is a favorable initial position for joining the aromatic rings into graphitic layers. This occurs after the release of hydrogen and nitrogen atoms from the molecules [84,85].

The reflection at position $\sim 31.1^\circ 2\theta$ corresponds to the graphite

Table 3

Elements detected by XPS (in at.%), flood gun (FG) setup, additional binding energy (BE) shift (in eV), and Si2p BE (in eV).

	Al	Si	O	C	FG setup	BE shift	Si2p BE
0.2An_MMT	5.3	17.4	34.1	43.1	1 V, 50 μ A	-0.2	103.4
0.4An_MMT	4.5	14.6	27.2	53.7	1 V, 50 μ A	-0.2	103.7
0.6An_MMT	4.7	16.1	30.5	48.7	1 V, 1 μ A	-0.3	103.4
0.8An_MMT	2.2	8.4	15.3	74.1	1 V, 1 μ A	-0.2	103.9

(002) planes having $d_{002} = 3.34 \text{ \AA}$ [1,48]. This is the indication of correctness of the assumption that the carbon prepared from low molecular weight organic compounds can have the graphitic structure.

Raman spectra confirm the presence of graphitic carbon in pyrolyzed samples (Fig. 3b). For higher clarity, the absolute values of the intensities were converted to relative values, i.e. the maximum value of each spectrum is 100 %.

All spectra contain disorder band (D; $\sim 1307 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), graphitic band (G; $\sim 1582 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), and graphite overtone band (2D; $\sim 2610 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), with the D bands being the most intense in all cases (Fig. 3b). However, the intensity of G bands, i.e. the graphitic character of produced carbon, increases with the increasing carbon content, and the intensity ratios of these bands (I_D/I_G) gradually decrease: 1.49 (0.2An_MMT), 1.30 (0.4An_MMT), 1.26 (0.6An_MMT), 1.21 (0.8An_MMT).

The I_D/I_G ratios for 0.4An_MMT and 0.6An_MMT are similar to the ratio $I_D/I_G = 1.28$ reported by Stimpfling and Leroux for 3-sulfopropyl-methacrylic acid/hydrocalcite composite pyrolyzed at $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [67]. Since Stimpfling and Leroux are the only ones reporting Raman spectroscopy results for carbon prepared from low molecular weight sources (numerical values only [67]), no other comparison is possible.

Weak bands ($\sim 1602 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) overlapping the G bands in Raman spectra of 0.4An_MMT - 0.8An_MMT samples indicate a presence of

nitrogen bound to aromatic carbon [86]. The presence of distinct 2D bands with intensity I_{2D} not exceeding the I_G indicates the presence of GBM, but not individual graphene layers [87]. The intensity of 2D band increases in spectra of samples with higher carbon content (0.4An_MMT - 0.8An_MMT) compared to 0.2An_MMT (Fig. 3b). This is reflected in I_{2D}/I_G ratios, i.e., 0.34 (0.2An_MMT), 0.74 (0.4An_MMT), 0.89 (0.6An_MMT), 0.83 (0.8An_MMT). The increasing intensity of 2D bands can be attributed to the increasing amount of GBM in the samples. In studies focused on the preparation of carbonaceous materials from macromolecular sources at temperatures of $400\text{--}1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, either no 2D bands [21,48,50] or very broad and extremely weak 2D bands [28,37,39,40,42,57] have been reported. At temperatures $>1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, whether comparable to $1300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($1200\text{--}1400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [23,43-45,59]) or significantly higher ($1600\text{--}2800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [23,25,27]), the 2D bands in the Raman spectra are narrower, more intense and distinct. In the case low molecular weight carbon sources, one can only speculate whether the carbonaceous materials prepared at temperatures of $500\text{--}600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [63,67], $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [29,35,36,61,62,66], $400\text{--}1100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [64], $700\text{--}1150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [65] or $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [60] would show the presence of 2D band if analyzed by Raman spectroscopy. It is certain that Stimpfling and Leroux [67] report no observation of 2D band. The temperature $1300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ used in our study is higher than the temperatures in studies focused on low molecular weight carbon sources. In view of the mentioned facts, however, this temperature can be considered suitable for the formation of graphitic structures in the prepared carbon.

The relatively high saddles between the D and G bands ($\sim 1400\text{--}1500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in spectra of samples 0.4An_MMT - 0.8An_MMT (Fig. 3b) can be attributed to the bands at $\sim 1420 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating also the presence of amorphous carbon [52,88,89]. High saddles can be observed in spectra of carbons prepared from macromolecular sources (gelatin [50], sucrose [40,49], polystyrene or polyethylene terephthalate [28], resol-F127 block copolymer [31], starch [57],

Fig. 4. C1s peaks in XPS spectra of pyrolyzed samples. (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

Table 4

Relative amount (in %) of individual components in C1s peaks, and full width at half maximum (FWHM; in eV) of the C=C component in C1s peaks.

	C=C	C-C/ C-H	C-OH/ C-O-C C=O	O-	C=O	π - π	FWHM of C=C
0.2An_MMT	61	38	0	0	0	0	1.2
0.4An_MMT	89	11	0	0	0	0	1.3
0.6An_MMT	98	1	0	0	0	1	1.0
0.8An_MMT	93	0	0	1	1	6	0.9

polybenzimidazole [37]), but none of these spectra have strong 2D bands similar to those in Fig. 3b and those reported for carbons prepared from nanocellulose [23,59].

Slightly stronger D band compared to the G band (Fig. 3b) was previously detected in Raman spectra of carbons prepared from sucrose [40], polyaniline [42], polyacrylonitrile [25,27], and nanocellulose fibers [23]. MMT was mostly used as the matrix in these studies [25,27,40,42], with the exception of carbon from nanocellulose where the yttrium-stabilized zirconia was used [23]. It can be stated that the Raman spectra of carbon prepared from anilinium are similar to many Raman spectra of carbons prepared from macromolecular precursors.

XPS measurements detected Al, Si, O, and C (Table 3; see also survey spectra in Fig. S4) which is in good agreement with the phases determined by XRPD analysis (Fig. 3a). A direct comparison of the C content detected by XPS analysis (surface analysis) with elemental analysis (bulk analysis) is not possible, but the lowest and highest C content in 0.2An_MMT and 0.8An_MMT, respectively (Table 3), corresponds to the trend observed in Table 2. The absence of N in the XPS data is another

confirmation of its nearly complete loss during pyrolysis (see discussion of elemental analysis results at the beginning of this section). The samples had significant charging behaviour indicating a limited electrical conductivity. The flood gun (FG) setup and additional small charge compensations are listed in Table 3. The flood gun setup was made on O1s peak to eliminate the charge effect (low binding energy (BE) broadening) and simultaneously minimize width of the peak by applying the lowest possible electron flood to avoid possible electron induced changes. The required FG current shows significant increase in electrical conductivity on samples 0.6An_MMT and 0.8An_MMT containing more carbon compared to samples 0.2An_MMT and 0.4An_MMT.

For a deeper understanding of the carbon structure in the samples, attention was paid to the high-resolution peaks of carbon C1s (Fig. 4). Because the character of the main single peak is typical for graphite sheets, literature data for such carbon-based materials were used [90]. The detailed study of the C1s peak was made with multiple components introduced: C=C at 284.5 eV (asymmetric shape), C-C at 285.0 eV, C-OH/C-O-C at 286.6 eV, C=O at 288.1 eV and O-C=O at 289.1 eV, expected π - π oscillations should be at 291.0 eV (symmetric shapes) [90]. The carbon related C1s peaks show minimum carbon to oxygen bonds and some defects of carbon ring at lower carbon content. The main components are carbon to carbon bonds when only the 0.6An_MMT and 0.8An_MM samples have provable π - π oscillations typical for carbon rings (Table 4). The increasing relative amount of C=C and π - π components together with decreasing relative amount of C-C/C-H component in the C1s peaks indicates an increase in the graphitic character of the produced carbon. This is consistent with the decreasing I_D/I_G ratios shown by Raman spectroscopy.

The C=C component of C1s peaks FWHM show low values about 1 eV for 0.6An_MMT and 0.8An_MM samples (Table 4). It can be a

Fig. 5. TEM images of pyrolyzed samples; a) 0.2An_MMT, b) 0.4An_MMT, c) 0.6An_MMT, d) 0.8An_MMT. Graphitic structures resembling bent stalks can be easily distinguished from monolithic grains. White arrows point to graphitic layers enveloping the grains. (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

Fig. 6. TEM images of pyrolyzed samples; a) 0.2An_MMT, b) 0.4An_MMT, c) 0.6An_MMT, d) 0.8An_MMT. White arrows indicate graphitic layers. Sites of measurements are labeled with numbers (see Table 5). (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

Table 5

Interlayer distance values (d_{002}) of graphitic carbon obtained from 11 measurements performed on TEM images (Fig. 6) by dividing the bar lengths by number of layers crossing the bar.

TEM image	meas.no.	length(nm)	Number of layers	d_{002} (nm)
Fig. 6a	1	1.054	3	0.35
Fig. 6a	2	1.640	5	0.33
Fig. 6a	3	0.630	2	0.32
Fig. 6b	1	3.645	11	0.33
Fig. 6b	2	2.709	8	0.34
Fig. 6b	3	2.641	8	0.33
Fig. 6c	1	2.716	8	0.34
Fig. 6c	2	3.410	10	0.34
Fig. 6c	3	1.693	5	0.34
Fig. 6d	1	4.805	14	0.34
Fig. 6d	2	2.791	8	0.35

consequence of higher conductivity similar to the already mentioned charge compensation current. The negligible (0.2 eV) additional BE shift of the spectra in CasaXPS (Table 3) suggests that the FG setup used was effective in the charge compensation.

The Si2p and Al2s peaks in high resolution spectra (Fig. S5) are weak due to the presence of high amount of carbon. Both Si and Al are at binding energies typical for oxides: Al2s at about 120 eV [91] and Si2p at about 104 eV [92]. Interestingly, the BE of the Si2p peak increases with the amount of carbon, except for the 0.6An_MMT sample (Fig. S5). This may indicate some change in the interaction of Si with carbon, since the BE calibration was performed on carbon. The Al2s peaks are of low intensity for similar evaluation (Fig. S5).

3.3. Morphology of pyrolyzed samples

TEM analysis (Fig. 5) allows to observe the graphitic structures. Resembling bent stalks or sheaves, they are easily distinguished from the

more or less oval monolithic grains. Their amount observable on TEM images (Fig. 5) increases with increasing w_{CP} (Table 2). Graphitic layers enveloping the silicate grains (as a lighter rim around a darker grain) are indicated by white arrows in Fig. 5c and d. Such a structure was previously observed in pyrolyzed samples of e.g. polypyrrole in MMT [45] or polyfurfuryl alcohol in TAE [54].

TEM images with a larger scale (Fig. 6) show in detail the graphitic structures formed by pyrolysis (white arrows in Fig. 6). Clear visibility of the layers enables direct measurement of their distance, i.e. another possibility to determine basal distances (d_{002}) supplementing the results of XRPD analysis (Fig. 3a). Numerical data from individual measurements performed on TEM images (Fig. 6) and resulting d_{002} values are listed in Table 5. The average value $d_{002} = 0.337 \pm 0.008$ nm corresponds to graphite [1,48] and agrees well with the results of XRPD analysis (see reflection $\sim 31.1^\circ 2\theta$ in Fig. 3a). Moreover, a number of observed graphitic structures having 10 or fewer graphene layers (Fig. 6, Table 5) can be classified as a multi-layer graphene [1]. Its presence in the samples is consistent with the observed 2D bands in Raman spectra (Fig. 3b).

TEM images in Figs. 5 and 6 are comparable to TEMs of materials obtained from macromolecular carbon sources (nanocellulose [23,59], polybenzimidazole [37], polypyrrole [45], polyfurfuryl alcohol [54], or lignocellulose [93]). In particular, the similarity of the formed graphitic layers on the surface of the grains with those shown in the literature [23, 37,45,54,59] is another confirmation that the use of low molecular weight carbon sources and the omission of the polymerization step does not hinder the formation of graphite and GBM.

3.4. Electrical conductivity of pyrolyzed samples

Considering the increasing values of w_{An} (Table 1) and w_{CP} (Table 2) and since XRD, Raman, XPS and TEM analyses showed the presence of graphite and GBM, electrical conductivity of the pyrolyzed samples was

Fig. 7. Electrical conductivity of pyrolyzed samples (according to Eq. (2)) in dependence on a) w_{An} (according to TGA) and b) w_{CP} (according to elemental analysis). (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

assumed. This assumption was confirmed by electrical conductivity measurements (Fig. 7). Dependence of the conductivity on w_{An} (Fig. 7a) and w_{CP} (Fig. 7b) is not linear and suggests that further increasing w_{An} and (after pyrolysis) w_{CP} above the already achieved values would not result in significantly higher conductivity for the preparation method used in this study. Fig. 7a shows where the curve changes from convex to concave: the inflection point corresponds to $w_{An} \approx 25$ wt%.

Nevertheless, it must be noted that while the conductivity of the sample 0.2An_MMT ($w_{CP} = 5.2$ wt%; Fig. 7b) is quite low ($\sigma = 0.03 \pm 0.01$ S m⁻¹), the other samples ($w_{CP} > 6.8$ wt%; Fig. 7b) exhibit an increase in conductivity of three to four orders of magnitude: 9.96 ± 1.28 , 23.88 ± 3.25 , and 35.26 ± 3.36 S m⁻¹ for 0.4An_MMT, 0.6An_MMT, and 0.8An_MMT, respectively.

Electrical conductivity values of our samples are comparable to those reported in several other studies describing the use of macromolecular carbon sources: ~ 0.03 S m⁻¹ (graphite from coal-tar pitch in coke [22]), 0.01 – 1 S m⁻¹ (graphite-like carbon from polyacrylonitrile in SEP [46]), ~ 1 S m⁻¹ (few-layered graphene from cellulose in alumina [59]), 10 S m⁻¹ (graphene-like carbon from sucrose in MMT [50]), 17 S m⁻¹ (thin, turbostratic graphite layers from cellulose in yttria-stabilized zirconia [23]).

4. Conclusions

The results of this study show that the use of macromolecular sources is not necessary for the *in situ* preparation of an electrically conductive nanocomposites containing silicates and graphitic carbon including GBM (multi-layer graphene in this case). Pyrolysis (1300 °C under Ar atmosphere) of low molecular weight carbon source (anilinium) in montmorillonite is sufficient for a nanocomposite of this type, while the morphology of the resulting carbon and the electrical conductivity of the nanocomposites are comparable to many materials prepared from macromolecular sources.

The usefulness of the obtained results lies in the possibility of utilizing the output of a common process – sorption of low molecular weight organic compounds on clays – for the preparation of electrically conductive material. Since clay sorbents are cheap, in practice they are not regenerated, a new clay is used instead, and the clay with organic substances becomes waste. There is the possibility of turning such waste into a useful product suitable e.g. as an additive for conductive ceramics.

Data availability

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11611605>.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Markéta Davidová: Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jonáš Tokarský:** Writing – review

& editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lenka Kulhánková:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Silvie Vallová:** Investigation, Data curation. **Lenka Reháčková:** Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Michal Ritz:** Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Martin Kormunda:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2024.119662>.

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